

Guidelines on onboarding policies during the EOSC Federation build-up phase

Version from 28 November 2025

EOSC Nodes¹ shall serve as community gateways to the EOSC Federation, for example by offering the capacity to onboard third-party resources. Onboarding resources and provision of onboarded resources generally remain (from the viewpoint of the EOSC Federation) a competence of the EOSC Nodes, which can set up their own onboarding policies and other related policies (e.g. access policy and acceptable usage policy) and measures.²

Consequently, at the level of the EOSC Federation and its governance, only the overarching guidelines for onboarding policies are outlined below, to which all EOSC Nodes must adhere to during the onboarding process or while provisioning onboarded resources. They are directed towards the EOSC Nodes, though some of the points (specifically those marked with *) might find their reflection in the onboarding policies of the EOSC Nodes directed towards the third-party resource providers to guarantee adherence with these overarching guidelines.

The subsequent guidelines will evolve during the build-up phase.³ They are:

Scope

- *Providers of onboarded resources must align with the purpose of the EOSC Federation and contribute to the key outcomes of the EOSC Federation outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook.⁴
- Onboarded resources shall be of relevance for the implementation of the suggested use cases or the realisation of federating capabilities or generally the activities of the Node during the build-up phase.

¹ The EOSC Federation is not in production mode yet. The EOSC EU Node is in production and offering its services since October 2024. During the first wave of building the EOSC Federation, 13 'candidate' EOSC Nodes joined the EU Node with voluntary contributions in building an operational EOSC Federation. More 'candidate' Nodes are expected to join in subsequent enrolments, with the aim to become EOSC Nodes when the EOSC Federation becomes operational. With this clarification, in this text for simplicity of language we will truncate the terms 'candidate' and 'build-up phase', e.g. instead of 'EOSC candidate Node' or 'governance of the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation' we will use the expressions 'EOSC Node' and 'EOSC Federation governance'.

² A template for such an onboarding policy could be worked out during the build-up phase and could be structured as follows: the scope of the policy, the onboarding requirements (e.g. eligibility criteria, technical and operational requirements), the onboarding modalities covering different cases of resources, the onboarding process, and governance and compliance.

³ It shall be made clear to third-party resource providers, that overarching guidelines and policies are being developed during the build-up phase and will change over time.

⁴ [EOSC Federation Handbook](#), Version 1, Chapter 1.

Onboarding process

- The selection of resource providers and integration of their resources shall be transparent and inclusive within the (national/thematic) community of the Node. Nodes shall publish selection criteria and operate a simple no-conflict-of-interest declaration and handling process.

Eligibility criteria

- *Providers of onboarded resources must agree to comply with the (evolving) minimal criteria for inclusion of resources in the EOSC Federation.⁵
- *Providers of onboarded resources shall show commitment for long-term sustainability of their onboarded resources, at least for 24 months.

Technical requirements

- *Providers of onboarded resources must agree to comply with the (evolving⁶) technical specifications regarding integration in the EOSC Federation in close collaboration with the EOSC Node, which can define appropriate transition times for the providers to adhere to them.
- *Onboarded resources must operate at minimum at a Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of 7 (Self-assessment by EOSC Node and third-party resource provider). TRLs are defined in the General Annexes of the Horizon Europe Main Work Programme.⁷

Operational requirements

- *For the EOSC Federation the EOSC Nodes must remain the primary contact point during either the onboarding process or the provision of onboarded resources.⁸ The EOSC Federation build-up group and the EOSC Tripartite Governance must remain informed

⁵ Minimal criteria for inclusion of resources in the EOSC Federation will be adopted by the EOSC Tripartite governance.

⁶ The technical specifications are defined and versioned by the EOSC Federation build-up group or in related interim governance bodies established through the MoU, see section on Governance.

⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/horizon-europe-work-programmes_en

⁸ A Node might either host the third-party resource itself or provide a link to a third-party resource, which remains hosted on the infrastructure of the third-party resource provider. Depending on the hosting location of the onboarded resources, different liability rules may apply. However, notwithstanding potential liability of the third-party resource provider, EOSC Nodes are the primary contact point and could remain liable vis-à-vis the end user for any resource they provide. Where applicable, liability allocation follows national law and contract. At present, end-user agreements are concluded at provider or EOSC Node level, while the EOSC Federation provides the coordination and trust framework.

about all onboarded resources from resource providers, their provenance and their performance (usage by local and Federation users, reliability), e.g. by collecting such information automatically through federating capabilities like a resource catalogue or monitoring mechanism.

- *For questions on onboarded resources, the primary point of contact for an EOSC user or stakeholders in the EOSC Federation remains the EOSC Node, to which the resource is onboarded to. This does not exclude that the provider, in agreement with the EOSC Node, offers direct support for its own onboarded resources.

Governance

- *Providers of onboarded resources are represented in the EOSC Federation build-up group or in related interim governance bodies established through the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) covering the interim operational phase of the envisaged EOSC Federation.⁹ This representation occurs through their EOSC Node(s). This does not exclude that the EOSC Node(s) may nominate representatives from a provider to join the work of the build-up group, its subgroups, or the MoU governance bodies on behalf of the EOSC Node(s).

⁹ Committees and subgroups established through the Memorandum of Understanding on Preparing Operational Integration within the envisaged EOSC Federation (2025).

